

Senior CMALT portfolio submission

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Contextual statement

I have over 25 years' experience working in higher education supporting and delivering teaching, learning and research. I am a chartered librarian but have spent most of my career as a trainer, focussing on the use of technology and the internet to support learning and research.

When I graduated in 1992 the internet was just starting to be used in universities. I was probably one of the last undergraduates to pay a typist to type up my dissertation (I'd visited the new computer lab in the basement of the library, but it was a cramped, pungent, and not exactly inviting environment). I worked for a year as a graduate trainee librarian at the University of Glasgow, who were already using the internet in its text-based form via command-line services and using email and shared calendars (which I later realised was advanced for the time). My interest in the potential of technology and the internet to revolutionise information access and sharing was born. For my master's in information studies in 1993-4 I learned about hypertext and databases, and I wrote my dissertation on the "World Wide Web: hints and warnings for searching the internet". When I started my first professional post as a librarian, I found my knowledge of these new technologies was highly valued, which led me to a staff training role. It was then that my second passion around training and staff development emerged.

My career has been directed by my commitment to these two passions – sharing of and access to information using technology, and the importance of staff development and training to do this. In 1998 I was fortunate enough to convert a temporary volunteer post at a new Jisc service called [Netskills](#) into a permanent job, where I worked on several national training programmes around the implementation of the internet in various contexts. I also worked closely with individual organisations and institutions to deliver bespoke training programmes, going beyond technical 'training' into considerations around policy, strategy, benefits, barriers etc. I developed an interest in information literacy and the librarian's role in teaching. I found I was drawn to roles to support others in developing skills in training and delivered many 'train the trainer' courses.

I have always struggled with the divisions around the differences between teaching and training, with some implying that training is a lesser lower-level Pavlovian process. I have

rarely run a training workshop without considering motivation, barriers, fears, benefits, values, critical thinking, reflection – it's rarely just about the technology.

I returned to libraries working within Newcastle University, seeing first-hand how technology was being used to support library services, teaching, learning and research throughout the institution and delivering teaching sessions in collaboration with academics. A new opportunity back at Jisc enabled me to step back into national-level work, this time around scholarly communication, supporting institutions to implement the new open access policies for journal article publishing.

In my early career the types of technology I used were more directly related to the learning environment i.e. using technology to deliver teaching and training. In later years I have been focussed on the research environment, making sure research outputs are discoverable and more recently ensuring that the whole research process itself is open. As research outputs are also learning resources, and teaching is informed by research, I consider my work is still within scope of CMALT.

My career has also shifted from delivering training to facilitating community learning – this enables a community to provide immediate support in a fast-changing environment and allows institutions to tailor approaches to their own needs.

Key themes across my career include the value of learning across communities, peer-learning, bringing communities together; the importance of information access and sharing; supporting others to develop training skills and finally sharing practical approaches.

I find that no matter which direction my career takes, some fundamental lessons from my early library career have stood me in good stead - developing skills in the 'reference interview', that is trying to work out what library users actually want and not just what they tell you they want. A key question I would use here, which is also invaluable when dealing with learning technology, is to ask, 'what are you trying to do'? I would invariably find out that what they were trying to do bore little relation to the question they asked! Similarly, it's easy to get carried away with the latest technologies, but you always need to ask 'what am I actually trying to do?'

I am submitting my portfolio for Senior CMALT for several reasons. I welcome the opportunity it provides to reflect on my career, both past and future. I would also like to share my experiences and receive recognition for the knowledge and experience I have gained. I welcome this opportunity to capture the key lessons I've learned in my career working in learning technology. Because I would like to reflect on my whole career, I have included links to inline examples from older work throughout, but unless stated, have only provided links to resources from the last 3 years in my evidence.

1: Operational Issues:

1a: An understanding of the constraints and benefits of different technology

Description

My early career in training at Netskills was to train others in the use of internet technologies for different applications in teaching and learning. I therefore needed to be aware of different technologies and their strengths and weaknesses. Jisc holds a neutral position in the sector and therefore our advice was valued due to its objectivity. I ran workshops on finding information on the web, including quality evaluation issues, using blogs and wikis and writing web pages using HTML and authoring tools. I was also involved in the roll-out of early virtual learning environments in many institutions. I therefore had to develop a good understanding of the benefits and constraints of a wide range of different technologies and their use in the learning, teaching and research. As I trained in different sectors (higher and further education, specialist colleges, adult and community learning, and public libraries), I needed to understand the benefits and constraints in different contexts. This could include issues around bandwidth, filtering, accessibility and cost.

In my latest role supporting open research/science I carried out a review of existing activities in online open science training in the European research community. This was part of the development of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), which aims to develop a web of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data and services. The review for the EOSC Synergy project was intended to inform the choice of learning platforms and tools the project would use, but also explore different approaches to online learning.

The review included many projects and initiatives and I conducted interviews with 20 representatives from these projects. The aim was to find out which technologies they used and why. Our project aimed to demonstrate the values outlined in the [EOSC Strategic Implementation Plan 2019](#) (p.5), including being focussed on research needs, community-drive, inclusive and respectful of diversity, accessible to all, open by default, closed where necessary, hands-on and participatory, transparent and trustworthy. These translated into a set of selection criteria used to decide on our platform(s).

Reflection

In the example above around selecting a platform and tools for EOSC Synergy, our first requirement was that the platform we chose needed to be open source and available for us to host ourselves. This was important in that we needed to demonstrate a commitment to open systems and not use proprietary technologies, which could lead to a danger of vendor lock-in. Many university systems hosting research outputs are owned by global commercial companies whose motives around ownership and exploitation of content and data are much discussed.

However, the decision to choose an open source platform needs to be balanced with the need to have the knowledge, expertise and resources to host and develop the platform or to support an external hosting solution. Our project had the resources to support the chosen platform (Moodle), but the knowledge and expertise had to be acquired by our systems team.

We chose Moodle as the most used open source learning management system and it was highly flexible in terms of incorporating other learning tools as plugins. It also has a very active user community meaning it's frequently updated and new plugins developed regularly.

We also needed a platform to be flexible in terms of import and export of content as one of key aims was to make our content reusable so it could be included in other education and training programmes. Moodle allows course exports and import of SCORM packages and a wide range of other content types. However, it does not export as SCORM and even if it did, this may not be suitable for many as editing SCORM packages is difficult. Therefore, in order to make our materials as fully re-usable as possible, we made 'raw' content available as text files including individual assets such as images and videos. We also developed a catalogue to enable users to find and filter resources.

However, in the end we acknowledged that simply making the resources available on the platform does not make them used and the issues around encouraging re-use are even more complex. It is important with the implementation of any learning technology (or technology in general), not to expect the technology to solve the problem in isolation. There are usually many underlying issues affecting adoption of technology (such as time, fear, skills, reward, incentives). In the end it comes back to the question 'what are you trying to do?' – sometimes the answer is technology, but rarely in isolation.

Evidence

- [EOSC Synergy Online Learning Handbook](#) – guidance on different content types and tools
- [EOSC Synergy WP6: Initial review of systems, initiatives and development of selection criteria of the online learning/training platforms and initiatives](#)

1b: Technical knowledge and ability in the use of Learning Technology

Description

I have used many tools and platforms over the years – various VLEs (some long-forgotten (WebCT) and some still in use such as Blackboard and Moodle), blogs, wikis, website content management systems, web authoring tools, Turnitin plagiarism detection and grading, and referencing software. In my role as a trainer I needed to learn to use these tools in order to teach others, being aware of features that may cause confusion. I also have used many technologies to facilitate and deliver training, project and community activities.

Reflection

Technology is in constant change – there is a need to keep an open mind and to keep learning and experimenting, which I try to do (I have recently created a Mastodon account but have yet to make the plunge and use it!). However, despite the ongoing change, there are fundamental skills which I have found invaluable when learning any new tool. These include a knowledge of HTML and Style Sheets which can be useful to customise many tools,

and information and file management skills (can you work out where the item you're working on is being saved? Can you find it again?). I used to find the latter was often the most difficult issue in training! Although the increasing shift to searching for files rather than browsing is making this issue less significant.

More non-technical skills are also essential for best use of learning tools – for example, writing for the web environment, while it may not be considered a 'technical' skill, is vital to creating effective learning resources. Use of in-built templates in learning technologies can provide pedagogic scaffolding.

Finally, an understanding of how to import and export content is invaluable to pre-empt technology change – can you get your content out of the system you're using when the next one comes along. This often requires familiarity with the use of the most simple file formats such as text or .csv files.

Evidence

- Learning management systems - Moodle Administrator and course developer for the [EOSC Synergy Moodle](#) platform
- WordPress – I am an administrator for the [Jisc research blog](#).
- Wikis – [LibTeachMeet](#) , [EOSC Future](#)
- A [tutorial](#) I developed on using the wiki using Articulate Rise
- Video editing – [OER22 video](#), basic video editing to add the OER Intro/ outro and adding subtitles.

1c: Supporting the deployment of learning technologies

Description

I have been involved in several training programmes to support the deployment of learning technologies at institutions. These have included the rollout of virtual learning environments at several universities. I was also involved in training for the [national rollout](#) of the Turnitin plagiarism detection service, in collaboration with the [Jisc Plagiarism Advisory Service](#). I co-delivered a 3-year programme of training to public library authorities as part of the rollout of the [People's Network](#). This covered various aspects of using the internet to support and enhance library activities.

More recently, I have supported the implementation of open access policies which have required institutions to make changes in systems and processes. Following the announcement of new open access requirements by funders beginning in 2016, UK institutions had to develop processes and systems to support researchers to deposit their research outputs in an appropriate repository and / or with an appropriate licence to enable sharing. Jisc's [Open Access Good Practice project](#) was a community-based support activity involving nine projects (30 universities plus a wider community of practice of more than 200 professionals from 90 universities). These projects produced advice, guidance, models, case studies and other support materials to help the higher education sector to implement open access as efficiently as possible. I started working on the project in 2015 and was involved in several community events and writing up the synthesis of the project outputs. As part of the

synthesis, several themes emerged covering the full range of activities affected by implementing new systems and approaches, including advocacy for OA, baselining to track progress, changes to structural workflows, cost management, policy compliance and finally technical issues around metadata, systems and interoperability. My role was to facilitate peer support and synthesise findings back to the community for implementation locally. One particularly useful technique to plan institutional change, which was used by the projects and that I subsequently used in workshops, was intervention mapping.

Intervention mapping

Problem	Goal (positive phrase)	GOALS OF CHANGE			ACTIONS
		<i>Knowledge</i>	<i>Attitude</i>	<i>System / process</i>	
	A positive, discrete achievable goal. This is the positive state you want to have achieved	Is there a gap in knowledge that's contributing to the problem? Whose lack of knowledge? If so what do people need to know?	Is it an opinion, belief or view on what others do which is influencing behaviour? Whose attitude? If so, what attitudes to people need to hold to address this?	Is there something technical, practical or organisational contributing to the problem? What is needed to enable people to act well?	What changes are needed to solve the problem? Plan your actions. Consider approaches, techniques or strategies to achieve the goals

Worksheet and facilitator's guide:
<https://radar.brookes.ac.uk/radar/items/67242129-b94b-4d1a-be80-a355974d976c/1/>

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As mentioned earlier, as part of the EOSC Synergy project I was involved in the design, development and deployment of a learning platform, incorporating a range of learning tools. Before developing the platform, I carried out an extensive review of existing activities in the open science training field, making recommendations as to the tools chosen. Through my previous knowledge of the administration of learning management systems, I was able to support the project systems administrator in tailoring the platform in terms of features, plugins and appearance. The initial systems and technology review is openly available along with the report on the final platform deployment (see evidence).

Reflection

My first reflection is that 'deployment' of technologies can mean different things to different people. In the software and application development field, it simply means getting something to work technically. However, ensuring the technology is deployed in the sense that it is used and used effectively is a different, and more complex, matter.

For example, while a good open access repository infrastructure is now in place, it took longer for the processes and support around those systems to be put in place to ensure researchers actually deposit their outputs. The interplay of rewards, incentives, institutional policies and processes along with technical infrastructure and tools, all affect successful deployment. Every institution is unique and faces different challenges, which must be considered when implementing learning technology.

One key lesson I have learned when deploying any new technology is to never assume that others can see the benefits – sometimes they really need to be spelt out and contextualised for an individual learner, using examples they will find relevant.

I have also learned never underestimate the fundamental technologies involved in deploying technology, such as access management. The ability to provide an easy and smooth login process is a key step to deploying any technology successfully. This proved to be an issue in EOSC Synergy, where one of the technical goals was to introduce federated EOSC authentication, but this made the login process complex and prevented access to certain content.

Evidence

- [EOSC Synergy Learn platform](#)
- [EOSC Synergy WP6: Initial review of systems, initiatives and development of selection criteria of the online learning/training platforms and initiatives](#)
- [EOSC-SYNERGY EU DELIVERABLE D6.2 Final release of the training platform including the self-deployable tutorials capabilities, and Hackathon-as-a-Service platform](#)
- [EOSC-SYNERGY EU Deliverable D6.3: Final report about skills development support activities and related services](#)

2: Learning, Teaching and Assessment processes

2a: An understanding of teaching, learning and/or assessment processes

Description

My background as a trainer required me to become familiar with pedagogy and instructional design approaches. This has been done through self-study, attending short courses, completing Newcastle University's Certificate in Academic Practice which led to Associate Fellowship of the Advance HE. Finally, and most significantly, I have learned from colleagues and from feedback from learners through creating and delivering training courses. I have also delivered several 'train the trainer' programmes, including an accredited [BTEC e-Learning Essentials](#) programme. These have all required me to teach others about the principles of teaching, learning and assessment.

While working as a librarian at a university I was involved in teaching workshops as part of academic courses, in collaboration with lecturers. I also taught on the Postgraduate Training programme and marked assessments using Turnitin grading system.

My role in the recent EOSC Synergy project was to provide support to others to create quality online learning and training resources. The technical service teams were tasked with creating training for their tools and I initially attempted a tailored approach to working with the teams to gauge their experience of training delivery. However, due to a lack of engagement I developed resources which could be used independently by the project teams, while being available to offer support and feedback. This led to the development of the EOSC Synergy Online Training Handbook, a Moodle course which could be worked through and then used as a reference. This covered basic concepts such as the ADDIE instructional design model, Bloom's taxonomy and how it relates to learning outcomes and

an introduction to assessment and evaluation. This online course contained training analysis and design forms to guide the process, which were based on the [ABC Learning Design](#) methodology including [Laurillard's six learning types](#).

The activities I developed on Analysis and Design were also delivered as part of data steward training courses, in collaboration with the FAIRsFAIR project, the Research Data Alliance and the CO-DATA summer schools. A key part of the data steward role is providing training to others, yet most staff in these roles have little or no experience of training.

Reflection

In my experiences over the last 18 months delivering short sessions (1.5-2 hours) on an introduction to pedagogy and training design I learned several lessons.

Firstly, many of these learners had little or no experience in training and so to avoid them feeling overwhelmed, I boiled the content down to the very essentials, which I captured in a 20-minute presentation, including interaction to bring in learner experiences and existing knowledge. I provided forms to allow learners to apply the learning and prompt thinking about the different aspects mentioned.

I found new trainers often focus too much on what they want to tell trainees and not think from the learner's perspective about the benefits and skills they will gain. Therefore, it is important to focus on learning outcomes – what the learner can do by the end of the training. In addition, assessment tends to be forgotten or just tagged on – the ABC LD process was useful for learners to reflect on their course designs in a visual way and provided a reminder to include both formative and summative assessment.

Finally, feedback from even experienced trainers highlighted that it's useful for everyone to have a reminder of core principles every now and then as it's easy to fall into bad habits.

Evidence

- [Introduction to pedagogy and training design video](#)
- [EOSC Synergy Online Training Handbook](#)
- [EOSC-SYNERGY EU DELIVERABLE: D6.1 Training materials and quality assurance guidelines](#)

2b: An understanding of your target learners

Description

I have run hundreds of training courses in my career and developed several online learning resources. As indicated previously, an understanding of target audiences is key to any activity. I have delivered training to a wide variety of audiences from different sectors including HE, FE, schools and public libraries. In my early career I was quickly introduced to the process of defining your learner audience which should then be used in conjunction with your learning outcomes, to design appropriate learning activities. I continue to use a planning form which guides me through this process.

In current projects I am developing and supporting others in the development of a range of workshops and short online courses. The planning process for both includes consideration

of audience and the template for the online course includes audience and pre-requisites. As part of the EOSC Future project I contributed to the development of different learning paths for different audiences.

Current training courses I deliver sessions on include the OpenAIRE Train the Trainer bootcamp and the EOSC Future Train the Trainer active learning course. For both courses the audience is specified in advertising and for the former, an application process is used to ensure the participants are appropriate for the level and content of the course.

For the EOSC Synergy project, the target audience of my 'train the trainer' guidance was primarily other project team members, who had the responsibility to create training on their services and technologies.

Reflection

One of the challenges of my career has been that it isn't always possible to get a really good understanding of my target learners. I often ran courses that were advertised publicly and while the course descriptions would specify a target audience and pre-requisites, it's hard to guarantee that attendees meet these in practice. In these situations there are various approaches I would use to try and get to know the learners better – mainly through the use of introductions to gauge the background and motivation of attendees. Building flexibility into the design of courses is helpful, for example including optional more advanced material, or allowing attendees to tailor tasks to their own contexts.

The EOSC Synergy project was challenging as I found it hard to engage project team members in developing training. Partly this was because their first priority was to develop their services before they could develop training, but also several members were not interested in training. In the early phases of the project the guidance I provided covered a wide range of training approaches allowing flexibility, but as the project progressed I realised the only mode of delivery would be asynchronous independent learning tutorials on Moodle. I therefore focussed on this method only, cut the pedagogical information down to key points and provided a Moodle template that could be used to structure the tutorials. I can't say these approaches worked completely, but I did my best to adapt to the audience's needs. However, in this case, the lack of incentive to produce training was key (producing training was not a KPI of the other work packages).

Evidence

- [Synergy handbook guidance on considering audiences](#)
- [EOSC Future learning paths](#)

3: The Wider Context: Understanding and engaging with legislation, policies and standards

3a: Understanding and engaging with legislation

Description

My work has required a knowledge of several aspects of legislation affecting learning technology and information sharing, including copyright and intellectual property, accessibility, health and safety and data protection.

The main area of legislation that has affected my work is around copyright and intellectual property, particularly the Copyright, Designs and Patents Act 1988. In my library work it was significant around advising staff and students on the amounts of a text that could be copied for study purposes and for putting together reading lists. In many of my training courses on e-learning, copyright was significant in terms of reuse of material, particularly around re-use of images where I would advise on sources of copyright free images. Copyright was also significant in my training and awareness of plagiarism issues, understanding the difference between plagiarism and breach of copyright.

In my recent work with open access and open research, copyright issues are at the fore, underpinning sharing of information, resources and data. Creative Commons licensing, which provides more flexibility to the 'All rights reserved' of many legal copyright statements, is central to the open 'movement'. In order to provide advice and guidance to others, I have had to develop a good understanding of the different Creative Commons licences and how they complement existing legislation. These licences are also part of funder requirements for open access.

Reflection

Legislation can be a great driver of change, providing the motivational 'stick' for behaviour change. However, it can also present barriers. The extra steps needed to comply with accessibility regulations for learning resources are time-consuming. Copyright legislation in particular can seem quite confusing which can hinder compliance with a 'head in the sand' approach taken. If licences are not clearly displayed on resources then that can prevent the resources being used.

When explaining copyright and licensing requirements for open access I found it helpful to link this to the question 'what do you want others to be able to do with your research?', explaining what each level of licence allows others to do with their research. With data sharing this brings up issues around Data Protection regulations, where sensitive data is not appropriate to share. This leads to discussions around exceptions to funder open access mandates and the concept of [FAIR data](#) (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), where FAIR data is more appropriate than open (i.e. it can be accessed under certain terms and conditions).

There is no getting away from the fact that legislation can be complex but linking to real world examples and facilitating community sharing have been key to my approach to supporting others.

Evidence

- [Synergy Learn instructions for Trainers](#) (includes guidance on accessibility, citing resources and licensing).
- Licensing your research <https://osc.cam.ac.uk/how-license-your-own-work> [as Helen Blanchett, 2015]

Open Data Cambridge @CamOpenData · 12h

Many thanks to @hblanchett from @Jisc for her excellent presentation yesterday about @creativecommons licences @Cambridge_Uni!

3b: Understanding and engaging with policies and standards

Description

The two areas I would like to highlight here are open access policies and technical metadata standards.

Firstly, the open access policy landscape in the UK has been fast-moving in recent years as funder policies for research outputs have evolved. Public policies (from Research Councils UK, then [UKRI](#)) and charity funders (such as [Wellcome](#)) have required research outputs to be made open access. This has been a core part of my role in recent years providing guidance and support to institutions in meeting these mandates, as detailed in section 1c.

In addition, I am increasingly involved in activities around influencing policies, with Jisc often providing input to policy consultations. In the EOSC Synergy project I was involved in the workpackage on policy, which included each country carrying out an initial landscape analysis of policies to support engagement with EOSC, followed by a gap analysis and a final report on progress. As co-chair of the [EOSC Association Task Force on Upskilling Countries to engage in EOSC](#), I facilitate sharing of policy approaches between countries.

Secondly, metadata standards and persistent identifiers (PIDs) are vital to efficient sharing of research outputs, which underpin the progress to open research. As part of the [UK ORCID support team](#), I facilitated ORCID members' days to enable institutions to share approaches to ORCID implementation. I am currently a member of the UK Research Identifier National Coordinating Committee ([RINCC](#)) which aims to shape the priorities of PID-related activities and policies in the UK. Standardised metadata is also important when sharing learning resources, particularly in a federated system such as EOSC, leading the EOSC Synergy project to use the [RDA minimal metadata profile for learning resources](#).

Reflection

As with legislation, policy is a great driver of behaviour change. However, there does need to be a consequence for non-compliance with policies. In the early days of OA policies, there were few consequences for non-compliance so uptake was slow. However, once OA policies were tied to [REF2021 submissions](#) (ie your research could only be submitted to REF if it was open access), this provided a massive motivator. However, the focus on outputs only as a measure of research quality is flawed and has led to research assessment globally being reviewed. In the UK, the Future Research Assessment Programme is exploring new approaches. This demonstrates the unintended consequences of policies and how they must adapt in response. I recently hosted a podcast about the FRAP programme, discussing its aims with representatives from the UK national funders.

It is also important to consider how policy is only one part of the system that is needed to support behaviour change. In an upcoming roundtable for professional and technical staff on their roles in supporting open research, I will refer to the [Centre for Open Science model of change](#) created by Brian Nosek, which places policy at the tip of a pyramid of factors necessary to support change, with the infrastructure of technologies and systems to 'make it possible' providing the foundation.

1 Center for Open Science Model of Change by Brian Nosek

Implementing technical standards is not straightforward either. Increasingly researchers have ORCID as they are required by funders or publishers, but there is a need for advice on making best use of it. For example, researchers may end up with more than one ORCID, defeating the point of it as a unique identifier. They may also not realise that in order for them and their institution to make the most of the efficiencies of using ORCID to automatically import / export their records, they need to grant permission to their institution to access their ORCID profile. These types of issues are the focus of advocacy activities in institutions.

Agreement on technical standards is a complex process and it can take quite some time for a global standard to emerge. In the meantime, projects and initiatives may develop a standard to harmonise other standards, thus creating yet another standard! Actually getting a standard to be used, for example providing metadata to describe research outputs, is difficult as it is time-consuming to create.

Evidence

- [EOSC-SYNERGY. EU DELIVERABLE: D5.1 National/International engagement plan with policy makers and funders](#)
- [EOSC-SYNERGY EU Deliverable D5.3: Feedback report on project policy recommendations](#)
- UK Research Identifier National Coordinating Committee (RINCC) – [notes from the last committee meeting](#) on 3rd November 2022
- EOOSC Engagement at the Regional Level – [Panel session outline](#); Presentation [Regional approaches in EOOSC Synergy](#) Symposium 17th November 2022
- [Research Talk: Exploring the assessment of UK research performance](#)

- [Open access briefing paper: The potential of global identifiers to support more efficient workflows for all kinds of OA](#) [2018, cited as Helen Blanchett]

4: Communication and working with others

4a: Communication and working with others

Description

Being a trainer requires the ability to communicate to different audiences which I have had to do working across a range of sectors. My strengths in communication have led to various roles making the most of this – including hosting webinars and community events (face-to-face and virtual), creating guides to Jisc services, writing articles with the press team, publishing books and hosting podcasts. Within Jisc I have had the role of explaining the various services we provide to support open research to our Relationship Management team who promote our services within institutions but are not able to be experts in the many services Jisc provides. I am currently focussing on developing my academic writing skills by working with project partners to produce journal articles for submission to peer-reviewed journals.

I have always enjoyed bringing people and communities together to exchange experiences and learn. When I worked as a librarian between 2011-15 I was involved in widening participation activities with local schools. In order to understand school teaching approaches better in order to support student transition to university, I started attending local TeachMeets, enabling me to network with teachers. I also presented activities around teaching to deter plagiarism and eventually collaborated with a local teacher on a conference presentation. I organised a couple of library teachmeets in Newcastle (ToonLibTM) and co-founded a Library TeachMeet wiki, to promote and share outputs. I am currently co-chair of the [OpenAIRE Open Science Training Co-ordinators Community of Practice](#) and have led development of the [Jisc Digital Research Community](#) (see Specialist Area 2).

Reflection

Communication and working with others have always been key themes throughout my career and areas I consider a strength, while always trying to improve. I try to adapt my communication style and language for different audiences and have strengths in making complex topics easier to understand. When explaining Jisc services to account managers, I received very positive feedback because I focussed on the issue or problem that the services solve for institutions, rather than describing what the service does. Once again, this brings to the fore the fundamental question of putting the problem first, not the technology.

With community work I have learned that facilitating communities is a difficult task and I am still developing skills in this area. I enjoy bridging gaps between communities, but there needs to be a shared motivation for the community to move beyond sharing to actual collaboration (see Specialist area 2). Working with European partners in an online environment has also enabled me to develop better collaborative skills, where issues of language, culture and technology may inhibit co-working. I actually find that my grounding

in training provides transferable skills in enabling me to be alert to the needs of different partners, to set clear goals for meetings, to keep focussed and keep to time, and to evaluate whether those goals have been met.

Evidence

- Invited to moderate the following event
 - <https://www.researchinformation.info/news/cispc-2020-uncovering-pandemic-library-strategies> (online)
- Podcasts
 - [Research Talk: Research environments of the future](#)
 - [Research Talk: Digital research infrastructure](#)
 - [Research Talk: Exploring the assessment of UK research performance](#)
 - [Research Talk: Achieving an integrated research management ecosystem](#)
- Community involvement
 - Jisc Digital Research Community – [Google Drive](#) with notes from monthly meet-ups with links to recordings and resources
 - OpenAIRE Open Science Training Co-ordinators Community of Practice – [rolling notes](#) (these meetings are not recorded but I chair them)

5: Specialist areas

5a: Specialist area 1: Best practices for online open research training

Description

My role in the EOSC Synergy project (2019-2022) was to lead a task on implementing approaches to creating quality online training. The project had this emphasis even before the shift online due to the pandemic. The project took a ‘train the trainer’ approach to online training in order to develop a scalable method to deliver the training needed to implement EOSC. As described elsewhere in this submission, I produced a handbook of how to deliver quality online training.

My approach throughout the project was highly collaborative and this led me to collaborations across projects and nations to explore best practices in delivering online training in open science. I was involved in several collaborations around different aspects of open science training, these included delivering training courses and carrying out research. These activities are listed in the evidence section, and I described many of these collaborations at a presentation at OER22 on ‘Collaboration across open science education’.

Reflection

Several themes have emerged from my experiences in open science training. When I first started the EOSC Synergy project, I was keen to explore whether anything was particularly different about delivering open science training online, as opposed to any other subject.

One of my initial reflections on the nature of open science training is that there are many communities involved, coming from different angles. Some communities have come from open data and open access and focus more on the technical skills involved in being open. Others come from the research integrity and reproducibility angle – that being open enables

transparency which can lead to better research. Until recently these communities have been separate but there are initiatives bringing both together (such as the UK Reproducibility Network's open research programme). I have done my small part to bridge these gaps, for example through inviting speakers to present across communities (for example, introducing the FORRT initiative which is made up of mainly early-career researchers focussing on embedding OS into taught curricula, to the OpenAIRE community, which is mainly EU projects and research infrastructures focussing on professional support staff such as librarians and data professionals).

As part of the leadership team for the global Reimagining Educational Practices for Open, we explored issues around the transition of the open science training community to the online due to COVID. The project explored how becoming part of a community is actually a goal of open science training, so training design needs to facilitate this.

There is a strong value-driven ethical dimension to open research training which is inclusive of different communities and conscious of the issues of equity and social justice. This presents issues for trainers in terms of 'practicing what you preach' ensuring training is FAIR itself. I have become involved in a couple of collaborations exploring how to translate the FAIR data principles into practical guidance for the creation of training materials. A particular area I have contributed towards is around accessibility – for FAIR data this means 'is it accessible in a repository?' but for training, accessibility has a very different meaning in terms of addressing different needs of learners. I will continue to explore, and facilitate in whatever way I can, the different approaches to open science training in different communities.

Evidence

- OER22 conference presentation [[Recording](#)]. Collaboration across open science education. Described collaborations throughout the development of the EOSC Synergy Learn platform
- [FORRT presenting at the OpenAIRE CoP](#)
- [Introduction to pedagogy and training design video](#)
- [EOSC Synergy Online Training Handbook](#)
- [ELIXIR FAIR Training Handbook – Make it accessible section](#)

5b: Specialist area 2: Facilitating digital research through community

Description

In 2020 I was involved in a consultation initiative within Jisc to inform its latest research strategy. An idea for a digital research community emerged and I was asked to take this forward. The intention was to enable discussion, sharing and collaboration around digital research related topics amongst staff involved in supporting the research lifecycle across institutions.

As a first step a community council was formed with representatives from different roles across the research lifecycle within institutions (researchers, research managers, IT, librarians, researcher developers), representatives from learned societies, national academies, professional bodies and funders. During the first six months I worked with the

council to identify and prioritise areas of activity for the community. With colleagues, I facilitated two online workshops to do this and I wrote a discussion paper synthesising the outputs and identifying the purpose of the community which is to:

- **Bringing communities together** – looking outward across disciplines, roles (researchers, research managers, librarians) and sector (industry, heritage). Somewhere that can help to knit initiatives together and connect stakeholders.
- **A place to share** research outputs and different examples of using technology for research
- **A place to address issues** raised in key themes, possibly through building a toolkit and curating content for the community. Other potential outputs need to be discussed.

The wider community was launched in December 2020 and currently has over 700 members across a Teams site and Jiscmail list. One of the most successful activities for the community has been the establishment of an informal virtual monthly meet-up. The sessions have included presentations of research projects addressing some aspects of using technology in research, discussions on how to address problems and collaboration cafes with Jisc services to give input to their development. Topics have included addressing digital research skills, archiving practice research, artificial intelligence, high performance computing and managing datasets.

Reflection

The most significant lesson I have learned from this activity is that communities don't just happen, they need to be supported to develop and grow. This is time-consuming and presents resourcing issues. In the case of this community, we were particularly affected by starting up in the early stages of the pandemic. While there was initial enthusiasm, we found that community members simply didn't have the capacity to engage and contribute as much as they wanted, and this worsened as the pandemic progressed. Following discussions with the council, we decided that Jisc should take a more guiding role in community activities rather than looking to the community to lead.

Jisc runs several communities for members and as a result we have developed our own internal community of community managers. This has been a great source of support and ideas. In developing my knowledge on community building, I have found the CSCCE community participation model extremely valuable in framing my work with communities:

2 CSCCE community participation model <https://www.cscce.org/resources/cpm/>

This helps me to understand the different roles community members may wish to take, depending on their knowledge of the subject and on the time they have available. This model isn't a continuum – community members may participate in different ways at different times. At a recent event half the audience left after the presentation section as they did not want to take part in the discussion! And that's fine.

I am aware of some issues that are likely to be preventing more cooperative and community led activity (in addition to the time and resource issue mentioned earlier). One strength of the community is that it aims to bring together people involved in different parts of the research process. However, this is also a weakness in that it can make finding common ground for collaboration difficult. For this type of sharing across discipline / role, the convey and contribute participation models may be most appropriate. As the digital research community matures, we are seeing it split into smaller groups focussed on specific topics with common interests. I hope that I can combine this approach with sharing to the wider community to raise awareness and understanding of the different roles digital technology plays in the research process.

A final reflection on the use of technology to facilitate this community. Obviously, online meetings have reduced barriers to participation compared to face-to-face, but we have had to navigate several challenges which may have inhibited community building. Our initial decision to use Teams to create a semi-private community space has proved to be problematic, with many members either not able to access Teams at all from their institution, or put off by the clunky way in which external guests access other Teams sites. We took the decision to move online meetings to Zoom, but continue with the Teams site in the hope that the technology will become smoother in future. We also use our old-

fashioned Jiscmail list as a core method of communication. We have had discussions within the community about whether the monthly meet-ups should be recorded for those who can't attend. We did not record any meet-ups at first, but shared presentations (if used) and comprehensive discussion notes. This was so we could create an informal atmosphere where members felt comfortable to contribute. We have compromised in some sessions where there is a distinct presentation which can be recorded (as long as the presenter agrees). However, the recording is made available via Zoom for 45 days until it is deleted – this aims to address increasing environmental concerns around the impact of storing unnecessary information.

Evidence

- [Digital research community page](#) – including list of council members
- [Discussion paper](#)
- [Google Drive of Monthly discussions](#)
- [Blog post summarising the research community launch](#)

6: Advanced area: National approaches to open science education

Description

Since starting work to support open access in 2015 I developed an interest in the various training needs around open research. This has involved three main strands of interlinked work. Firstly, sharing best practices for open research training (as described in Specialist area 1). Secondly, exploring skills for professional staff supporting open research as new roles have emerged. Finally, supporting national education programmes on open research training, including working in Europe to facilitate sharing between projects and across nations. While I have touched upon some of these activities earlier in my portfolio, I have selected this as my advanced area as I am working at a different level on these initiatives, influencing national approaches and policies.

My role in supporting open access implementation led to co-founding the Open Research Competencies Coalition (originally the Scholarly Communications Competencies Coalition, formed in 2017). This was initially to address the issue of several emerging roles in this area, with little training available and no career path or recognition. This is an informal initiative where organisations who have a stake in open research training meet to share activities and identify areas for collaboration. Our activities have included mapping the skills and competencies required for scholarly communication and open research support roles, analysis of job descriptions (which vary from institution to institution) and collecting together useful links for professional development. We are currently collaborating with the UK Reproducibility Network to produce a series of 'primers' on working in open research support roles, to complement [their existing primers](#) aimed primarily at researchers. I am also working with the lead of the UKRN open research programme to co-facilitate a roundtable in February 2023 for representatives of professional and technical roles to

discuss how best to develop and recognise their roles in open research. I hope that this roundtable will lead to further work on recognising the contributions of professional and technical support roles and providing support for career development.

For my European work, in my new role as Senior e-Infrastructure Strategy Manager (skills) which began at the time I started the EOSC Synergy project, I was able to start thinking more strategically about implementing open research and the policy drivers which support training (described earlier in section 3b). I sat on the [EOSC Skills and Training Working Group](#) in 2020 and contributed to the [Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science report](#) which has influenced future EOSC work.

I currently have a more significant role as co-chair of the EOSC Association Task Force on Upskilling Countries to Engage in EOSC. Through this task force we share approaches to open science education and policy along with being consulted by the EOSC Association to influence its [Multi-Annual Roadmap](#) and the [Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda](#), which in turn influences the calls for Horizon Europe funding.

A key achievement of mine in 2021 was to bring all these initiatives together to discuss '[Advancing the skills agenda for reproducibility, open and FAIR](#)', a joint virtual UK national roadshow with ORCC, EOSC Synergy and a sister EOSC project, FAIRsFAIR.

Reflection

These activities have shown me the difficulties in coordinating anything nationally, ensuring the perspectives of so many different stakeholders are considered. The broad nature of open research makes this even more complex, particularly when it comes to defining a 'core' curriculum. It is also important to recognise that open research involves a shift in culture, which needs to be facilitated by reward and incentive structures. Once again, Brian Nosek's model of change is relevant.

Being able to progress national programmes also requires resources. Being able to engage funders and tap into their priorities is vital and something that ORCC struggled with, relying on volunteer effort. However, the UK Reproducibility Network were successful in securing funding so this demonstrates the need to be flexible to take opportunities where they come and collaborate. It is also difficult to gain recognition and professionalise new roles, so learning from other professions is vital, for example Research Software Engineers.

In terms of international approaches, while sharing is extremely valuable, it is important to note that experiences do not necessarily translate from one country to another and that there is no one 'best' way to implement open research education and policy.

To address core values in my advanced area, I feel I demonstrate these as follows:

- ***A commitment to exploring and understanding the interplay between technology and learning*** – through
- ***A commitment to keep up to date with new technologies*** – the nature of open research with its dependencies on technology to facilitate it, means that it is constantly changing and I am required to keep up.

- **An empathy with and willingness to learn from colleagues from different backgrounds and specialist areas** - Demonstrated through bringing together colleagues from different professions involved in supporting open research and learning from other initiatives in different countries.
- **A commitment to communicate and disseminate effective practice** – through facilitating ORCC meetings and wider events such as the national roadshow and conference presentations.

Evidence

- [ORCC / Synergy / FAIRsFAIR roadshow report ‘Coordination needed – a recurring theme from a recent UK workshop on open research skills’](#)
- EOSC Future presentation on national approaches – [UK National perspective on training and services to support FAIR and Open Science](#).
- [Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science report](#)
- [Summary of ORCC work](#) and [ORCC member list](#)
- EOSC Engagement at a National Level, EOSC Symposium November 17th 2022. Presentation on [‘Sustaining Momentum beyond the Tripartite events’](#) [PDF] on behalf of the EOSC Association Task Force on Upskilling Countries to Engage in EOSC.
- EOSC Engagement at a Regional Level, EOSC Symposium November 17th 2022. Presentation on [Regional Approaches in EOSC Synergy](#) [PDF]. [[Recording](#), starting at 40:05] – importance of common infrastructure and quality assurance

Future plans

My future development plans include improving how I record and share my experiences. While I am proactive in sharing through community activities, I would like to improve my reflective abilities, improve my knowledge of research methods and publish more in academic journals. I am also exploring different options for gaining a PhD around the topics I have covered in this portfolio.

I will continue to work on innovative projects which explore new developments in promoting open research – this is an area to which I feel committed and I would also like to continue and perhaps extend, the international aspect of my work. I will also continue to play my part in coordination of activities across the range of projects I’m involved in on a national and international level.

Several projects are shifting focus to incentivising open research practices and my work will increasingly involve research assessment and broader issues around research integrity, research quality and culture. I am working on the [Open and Universal Science](#) project (OPUS) which is exploring interventions to incentivise open research and partners including UNESCO who are looking at creating policy recommendations. I am also involved in an emerging international network called the [Network for Education and Research Quality](#) (NERQ), to be launched on March 3rd 2023, where I will be leading the Open Science Special Interest Group.

I am looking forward to leading on Jisc's activities around research skills and culture which will lead me to closer working with funders and strategic bodies. I am currently drawing up an operating plan for consultation with our stakeholder forums to develop Jisc's support in this area.

Confirmation and (optional) nominated assessor

Confirmation

I declare that, to the best of my knowledge, the statements and evidence included in this submission accurately describe my practice and are drawn from my own work, with the input and support of others duly and clearly recognised.

Signed: Helen C Clare

Date: 31 January 2023

Licencing and sharing

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